

QUIZ – electric propulsion

Check your expertise in electric propulsion & learn new facts about Horizon 2020 project GIESEPP MP.

How many of these questions can you answer correctly?

The correct answers you will find on the last page.

Answer these questions

1. What would be the two major aspects that guide the selection of an orbital propulsion system for one application?

- a) List price & availability of the system
- b) Time to orbit & wet mass of the system
- c) Technology & maturity of the system
- d) Origin & experience with the supplier of the system

2. What is a typically completely different requirement of an EP system for a GEO platform compared to a LEO platform?

- a) Size
- b) Delta V
- c) Lifetime
- d) Propellant

3. What is today much more in focus of a modern propulsion system than it used to be in the past?

- a) Marketing
- b) Reliability
- c) Low power consumption
- d) Price

4. What is the ratio between Full Electric, hybrid and Full Chemical propulsion in average for Starlink, One Web and Telesat constellations?

- a) 33%; 33%; 33%
- b) 66%; 33%; 0%
- c) 100%; 0%; 0%

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5. What are the two main stages where electric propulsion are commonly used on S/C?

- a) Re-entry and fine positioning
- b) Transfer to final orbit and station keeping or drag compensation
- c) Fine positioning (<1m) and station keeping or drag compensation
- d) Only transfer to final orbit

6. What are the 5 main parameters to size the number of thrusters for a telecom S/C?

- a) S/C dry mass, S/C Available electric power, thruster Impulse, duration of orbit transfer and thrust
- b) Propellant Flow regulation accuracy and Electronic unit efficiency
- c) Only electronic unit efficiency
- d) Propellant Flow regulation accuracy, thruster Impulse and thrust

7. What are the main advantages of RIT 2X compared to Hall Effect Thruster?

- a) Propellant mass savings and high specific impulse
- b) Propulsion units mass savings
- c) Propulsion units mass savings and space pollution
- d) Space pollution and propellant mass savings

8. Why do the cryopumps, in contrast to e.g. turbomolecular pumps, have to be switched off and warmed up at regular intervals during tests with radio-frequency ion thrusters?

- a) The connected compressor is not designed for continuous operation
- b) The running cryopump acts as a source of interference for the RF current responsible for the power coupling into the thruster
- c) The capacity of the cryopumps is limited, so the cryopumps must be regenerated

9. Which of the following plasma properties can be determined with the help of a near-field Faraday probe?

- a) The shape of the radial plasma density distribution
- b) The electron temperature in the discharge vessel
- c) The ion energy in the thruster plume

10. Why do charge exchange processes play a key role in modelling grid erosion?

- a) Slow charge exchange ions are attracted to the negatively biased grid of the thruster and sputter material there on impact.
- b) The charge exchange processes significantly change the neutral gas density in the discharge vessel. The plasma responds to this change by changing the electron temperature and ion density. This changes the ion optics in the grid system.
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11. What are the most relevant functions of a PPU in an EPS?

- a) To ignite the main chamber of the thruster
- b) To control the thrust through the beam current and voltages
- c) To protect the system against unexpected events or failures
- d) All of the above

12. From an industrialization point of view, what is the most critical aspect of a PPU?

- a) The use of Gallium Nitride transistors
- b) The use of digital control
- c) Automatic manufacturing and testing processes
- d) Use of any type of COTS, as long as they are cheap

Correct answers

1. b; 2. c; 3. d 4. c 5. b 6. a 7. a 8. c 9. a 10. a 11. d 12. c

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